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Group S_4 Difference Cordial Labeling

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Abstract

Objective: To find the Group S_4 difference cordial labeling of some standard graphs. **Method:** Path, Cycle and some standard graphs are converted into Group S_4 difference cordial graphs by labeling the vertices with the elements of S_4 and the edges as the difference of the order of the elements labeled to the vertices of the graph. **Findings:** Group S_4 difference cordial labeling for path, cycle and some standard graphs. **Novelty:** Graph labeling can use for issues in Mobile Adhoc Networks such as connectivity, scalability, routing, modeling the network and simulation. In this paper we compute the new concept of Group S_4 difference cordial labeling and also we prove that some standard graphs are Group S_4 difference cordial graph.

AMS Subject Classification 2010: 05C78

Keywords: Difference cordial Labeling; Path; cycle; Bistar; Comb; Ladder; S_4

1 Introduction

Graphs consider here are finite, simple, connected and undirected. Kala et. al defined group cordial prime labeling and also proved that many graphs satisfy group prime cordial labeling⁽¹⁻³⁾. Lourdusamy et. al introduced the concept of group S_3 cordial remainder labeling⁽⁴⁾. Results on group S_3 cordial remainder labeling can be found in⁽⁵⁻⁷⁾⁽⁸⁾. Group Q_8 difference cordial labeling⁽⁹⁾ was introduced by Lourdusamy et al. In this paper we introduce the new labeling called group S_4 difference cordial labeling. Here we prove that path, cycle, bistar, comb, crown and ladder related graphs admit group S_4 difference cordial labeling.

2 S_4 Difference Cordial Labeling

$S_4 = \{e, a, b, c, d, f, g, h, i, j, k, l, m, n, o, p, q, r, s, t, u, v, w, x\}$ is the group of all permutations of 4 elements set, where

$$e = (1), a = (12), b = (13), c = (14), d = (23), f = (24), g = (34), h = (12)(34),$$

$i = (13)(24), j = (14)(23), k = (123), l = (132), m = (234), n = (243), o = (134),$
 $p = (143), q = (124), r = (142), s = (1234), t = (1243), u = (1432), v = (1324),$
 $w = (1342), x = (1423).$

It has one 1 order element {e}, nine 2 order elements {a,b,c,d,f,g,h,i,j}, eight 3 order elements {k,l,m,n,o,p,q,r} and six 4 order elements {s,t,u,v,w,x}.

Definition 2.1. Let $\alpha: V(G) \rightarrow S_4$ be a function. For each edge xy assign the label 0 if $(o(\alpha(x)) - o(\alpha(y))) = 0\alpha$ is called group S_4 difference cordial labeling if $|v_\alpha(\lambda) - v_\alpha(\mu)| \leq 1$ and $|e_\alpha(0) - e_\alpha(1)| \leq 1$, where $v_\alpha(\lambda)$ and $e_\alpha(y)$ respectively denote the number of vertices labeled with an element λ and number of edges labeled with $y(y=0,1)$. A graph G which admits group S_4 difference cordial labeling is called group S_4 difference cordial graph.

3 Main Results

Theorem 3.1. The path P_n is S_4 difference cordial graph.

Proof. Let $V(P_n) = (v_\beta : 1 \leq \beta \leq n)$ and $E(P_n) = (v_\beta v_{\beta+1} : 1 \leq \beta \leq n-1)$. Define $\alpha: V(P_n) \rightarrow S_4$ be the vertex label as follows:

Let $n \equiv \gamma \pmod{24}$

$$\alpha(v_\beta) = \begin{cases} a \text{ if } \beta \equiv 1 \pmod{24} \\ b \text{ if } \beta \equiv 2 \pmod{24} \\ k \text{ if } \beta \equiv 3 \pmod{24} \\ l \text{ if } \beta \equiv 4 \pmod{24} \\ s \text{ if } \beta \equiv 5 \pmod{24} \\ t \text{ if } \beta \equiv 6 \pmod{24} \\ c \text{ if } \beta \equiv 7 \pmod{24} \\ d \text{ if } \beta \equiv 8 \pmod{24} \\ m \text{ if } \beta \equiv 9 \pmod{24} \\ n \text{ if } \beta \equiv 10 \pmod{24} \\ u \text{ if } \beta \equiv 11 \pmod{24} \\ v \text{ if } \beta \equiv 12 \pmod{24} \\ f \text{ if } \beta \equiv 13 \pmod{24} \\ g \text{ if } \beta \equiv 14 \pmod{24} \\ o \text{ if } \beta \equiv 15 \pmod{24} \\ p \text{ if } \beta \equiv 16 \pmod{24} \\ w \text{ if } \beta \equiv 17 \pmod{24} \\ x \text{ if } \beta \equiv 18 \pmod{24} \\ h \text{ if } \beta \equiv 19 \pmod{24} \\ i \text{ if } \beta \equiv 20 \pmod{24} \\ q \text{ if } \beta \equiv 21 \pmod{24} \\ r \text{ if } \beta \equiv 22 \pmod{24} \\ e \text{ if } \beta \equiv 23 \pmod{24} \\ j \text{ if } \beta \equiv 0 \pmod{24} \end{cases}$$

If $n = 24z + r, z \geq 0, 0 \leq \gamma \leq 23$. Here the elements of S_4 which are labelled to the first γ vertices from v_1 to v_γ are labeled $z + 1$ times and the remaining $24 - \gamma$ elements of S_4 are labeled z times.

So, $(v_\alpha(\lambda) - v_\alpha(\mu)) \leq 1$.

Further

$$e_\alpha(0) = \begin{cases} \lfloor \frac{24z + (\gamma - 2)}{2} \rfloor + 1 \text{ if } \gamma \text{ is even } \gamma \neq 0 \\ \lfloor \frac{24z + (\gamma - 2)}{2} \rfloor \text{ if } \gamma \text{ is odd} \end{cases}$$

$$e_\alpha(1) = \begin{cases} \lfloor \frac{24z + (\gamma - 2)}{2} \rfloor \text{ if } \gamma \text{ is even } , \gamma \neq 0 \\ \lfloor \frac{24z + (\gamma - 2)}{2} \rfloor + 1 \text{ if } \gamma \text{ is odd} \end{cases}$$

This implies that $(e_\alpha(0) - e_\alpha(1)) \leq 1$. Hence α is S_4 difference cordial graph.

Theorem 3.2. The cycle C_n is

Proof. Let $V(C_n) = (v_\beta : 1 \leq \beta \leq n)$ and $E(C_n) = (v_\beta v_{\beta+1} : 1 \leq \beta \leq n-1) \cup (v_1 v_n)$. Define $\alpha: V(C_n) \rightarrow S_4$ be the vertex label as follows:

Let $n \equiv \gamma \pmod{24}$

Case 1. $\gamma \neq 2, 0 \leq \gamma \leq 23$.

$$\alpha(v_\beta) = \begin{cases} e & \text{if } \beta \equiv 1 \pmod{24} \\ a & \text{if } \beta \equiv 2 \pmod{24} \\ b & \text{if } \beta \equiv 3 \pmod{24} \\ c & \text{if } \beta \equiv 4 \pmod{24} \\ k & \text{if } \beta \equiv 5 \pmod{24} \\ l & \text{if } \beta \equiv 6 \pmod{24} \\ s & \text{if } \beta \equiv 7 \pmod{24} \\ t & \text{if } \beta \equiv 8 \pmod{24} \\ d & \text{if } \beta \equiv 9 \pmod{24} \\ f & \text{if } \beta \equiv 10 \pmod{24} \\ m & \text{if } \beta \equiv 11 \pmod{24} \\ n & \text{if } \beta \equiv 12 \pmod{24} \\ u & \text{if } \beta \equiv 13 \pmod{24} \\ v & \text{if } \beta \equiv 14 \pmod{24} \\ g & \text{if } \beta \equiv 15 \pmod{24} \\ h & \text{if } \beta \equiv 16 \pmod{24} \\ o & \text{if } \beta \equiv 17 \pmod{24} \\ p & \text{if } \beta \equiv 18 \pmod{24} \\ w & \text{if } \beta \equiv 19 \pmod{24} \\ x & \text{if } \beta \equiv 20 \pmod{24} \\ i & \text{if } \beta \equiv 21 \pmod{24} \\ j & \text{if } \beta \equiv 22 \pmod{24} \\ q & \text{if } \beta \equiv 23 \pmod{24} \\ r & \text{if } \beta \equiv 0 \pmod{24} \end{cases}$$

If $n = 24z + r, z \geq 0, 0 \leq \gamma \leq 23$ and $\gamma \neq 2$. In view of the above labeling, we get

$$e_\infty(0) = \begin{cases} \left\lfloor \frac{24z+\gamma}{2} \right\rfloor + 1 & \text{if } \gamma \text{ is even} \\ \left\lfloor \frac{24z+(\gamma-1)}{2} \right\rfloor & \text{if } \gamma \text{ is odd } \gamma \neq 1 \\ \frac{24z}{2} + 1 & \text{if } \gamma = 1 \end{cases}$$

and

$$e_\infty(1) = \begin{cases} \left\lfloor \frac{24z+\gamma}{2} \right\rfloor & \text{if } \gamma \text{ is even, } \gamma \neq 0 \\ \left\lfloor \frac{24z+(\gamma-1)}{2} \right\rfloor + 1 & \text{if } \gamma \text{ is odd } \gamma \neq 1 \\ \frac{24z}{2} & \text{if } \gamma = 1 \end{cases}$$

Case 2. $\gamma = 2$. Let $n = 24z + 2$. Starting from v_1 every consecutive 24 vertices are labeled same as Case 1. The remaining 2 vertices are labeled with a, e. In view of the above labeling, we get

$$e_\infty(0) = e_\infty(1) = \frac{24z+\gamma}{2}.$$

In the above two cases, $(e_\infty(0) - e_\infty(1)) \leq 1$. Hence the cycle C_n is S_4 difference cordial graph.

Theorem 3.3. The comb graph $P_n \odot K_1$ is S_4 difference cordial graph.

Proof. Let the vertex set of $P_n \odot K_1$ be $\{v'_1, v'_2, \dots, v'_n, v''_1, v''_2, \dots, v''_n\}$ and $E(P_n \odot K_1) = \left(v'_\beta v'_{\beta+1} : 1 \leq \beta \leq n-1 \right) \cup \left(v'_\beta v''_\beta : 1 \leq \beta \leq n \right)$. Let $\infty: V(P_n \odot K_1) \rightarrow S_4$ be defined by,

$$\alpha(v'_\beta) = \begin{cases} a \text{ if } \beta \equiv 1 \pmod{12} \\ k \text{ if } \beta \equiv 2 \pmod{12} \\ s \text{ if } \beta \equiv 3 \pmod{12} \\ c \text{ if } \beta \equiv 4 \pmod{12} \\ m \text{ if } \beta \equiv 5 \pmod{12} \\ u \text{ if } \beta \equiv 6 \pmod{12} \\ f \text{ if } \beta \equiv 7 \pmod{12} \\ o \text{ if } \beta \equiv 8 \pmod{12} \\ w \text{ if } \beta \equiv 9 \pmod{12} \\ h \text{ if } \beta \equiv 10 \pmod{12} \\ j \text{ if } \beta \equiv 11 \pmod{12} \\ q \text{ if } \beta \equiv 0 \pmod{12} \end{cases}$$

$$\alpha(v''_\beta) = \begin{cases} b \text{ if } \beta \equiv 1 \pmod{12} \\ l \text{ if } \beta \equiv 2 \pmod{12} \\ t \text{ if } \beta \equiv 3 \pmod{12} \\ d \text{ if } \beta \equiv 4 \pmod{12} \\ n \text{ if } \beta \equiv 5 \pmod{12} \\ v \text{ if } \beta \equiv 6 \pmod{12} \\ g \text{ if } \beta \equiv 7 \pmod{12} \\ p \text{ if } \beta \equiv 8 \pmod{12} \\ x \text{ if } \beta \equiv 9 \pmod{12} \\ i \text{ if } \beta \equiv 10 \pmod{12} \\ e \text{ if } \beta \equiv 11 \pmod{12} \\ r \text{ if } \beta \equiv 0 \pmod{12} \end{cases}$$

Let $n = 12z + \gamma$ where $z \geq 0$ and $0 \leq \gamma \leq 11$. In view of the above defined labeling pattern, we observe that

$$e_\infty(0) = 12z + \gamma, e_\infty(1) = 12z + \gamma - 1.$$

Hence comb graph is S_4 difference cordial graph.

Theorem 3.4. Bistar $B_{n,n}$ is S_4 difference cordial graph.

Proof. Let y and z be the apex vertices and $y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n$ be the pendent vertices. We define $\alpha: V(B_{n,n}) \rightarrow S_4$ as follows:

$$\alpha(y) = a, \alpha(z) = k;$$

for $0 \leq \beta \leq n$,

$$\alpha(y_\beta) = \begin{cases} b \text{ if } \beta \equiv 1 \pmod{12} \\ c \text{ if } \beta \equiv 2 \pmod{12} \\ d \text{ if } \beta \equiv 3 \pmod{12} \\ f \text{ if } \beta \equiv 4 \pmod{12} \\ g \text{ if } \beta \equiv 5 \pmod{12} \\ h \text{ if } \beta \equiv 6 \pmod{12} \\ i \text{ if } \beta \equiv 7 \pmod{12} \\ l \text{ if } \beta \equiv 8 \pmod{12} \\ n \text{ if } \beta \equiv 9 \pmod{12} \\ p \text{ if } \beta \equiv 10 \pmod{12} \\ j \text{ if } \beta \equiv 11 \pmod{12} \\ k \text{ if } \beta \equiv 0 \pmod{12} \end{cases}$$

and

$$\alpha(z_\beta) = \begin{cases} s \text{ if } \beta \equiv 1 \pmod{12} \\ t \text{ if } \beta \equiv 2 \pmod{12} \\ u \text{ if } \beta \equiv 3 \pmod{12} \\ v \text{ if } \beta \equiv 4 \pmod{12} \\ w \text{ if } \beta \equiv 5 \pmod{12} \\ x \text{ if } \beta \equiv 6 \pmod{12} \\ e \text{ if } \beta \equiv 7 \pmod{12} \\ m \text{ if } \beta \equiv 8 \pmod{12} \\ o \text{ if } \beta \equiv 9 \pmod{12} \\ q \text{ if } \beta \equiv 10 \pmod{12} \\ r \text{ if } \beta \equiv 11 \pmod{12} \\ a \text{ if } \beta \equiv 0 \pmod{12} \end{cases}$$

Clearly,

$$e_\infty(0) = \begin{cases} n+1 & \text{if } n \text{ is multiple of } 11 \\ n & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$e_\infty(1) = \begin{cases} n & \text{if } n \text{ is multiple of } 11 \\ n+1 & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Hence ∞ is group S_4 difference cordial labeling.

Theorem 3.5. Ladder L_n is S_4 difference cordial graph.

Proof. Let $V(L_n) = \{v'_\beta, v''_\beta : 1 \leq \beta \leq n\}$ and $E(L_n) = \{v'_\beta v''_\beta : 1 \leq \beta \leq n\} \cup \{v'_\beta v'_{\beta+1}, v''_\beta v''_{\beta+1} : 1 \leq \beta \leq n-1\}$.

Define $\infty : V(L_n) \rightarrow S_4$ as follows:

$$\infty(v'_\beta) = \begin{cases} k \text{ if } \beta \equiv 1 \pmod{12} \\ l \text{ if } \beta \equiv 2 \pmod{12} \\ a \text{ if } \beta \equiv 3 \pmod{12} \\ s \text{ if } \beta \equiv 4 \pmod{12} \\ t \text{ if } \beta \equiv 5 \pmod{12} \\ u \text{ if } \beta \equiv 6 \pmod{12} \\ e \text{ if } \beta \equiv 7 \pmod{12} \\ j \text{ if } \beta \equiv 8 \pmod{12} \\ n \text{ if } \beta \equiv 9 \pmod{12} \\ o \text{ if } \beta \equiv 10 \pmod{12} \\ p \text{ if } \beta \equiv 11 \pmod{12} \\ r \text{ if } \beta \equiv 0 \pmod{12} \end{cases}$$

$$\infty(v''_\beta) = \begin{cases} m \text{ if } \beta \equiv 1 \pmod{12} \\ b \text{ if } \beta \equiv 2 \pmod{12} \\ c \text{ if } \beta \equiv 3 \pmod{12} \\ d \text{ if } \beta \equiv 4 \pmod{12} \\ v \text{ if } \beta \equiv 5 \pmod{12} \\ f \text{ if } \beta \equiv 6 \pmod{12} \\ g \text{ if } \beta \equiv 7 \pmod{12} \\ h \text{ if } \beta \equiv 8 \pmod{12} \\ i \text{ if } \beta \equiv 9 \pmod{12} \\ q \text{ if } \beta \equiv 10 \pmod{12} \\ w \text{ if } \beta \equiv 11 \pmod{12} \\ x \text{ if } \beta \equiv 0 \pmod{12} \end{cases}$$

We observe that,

Let $s = \lfloor \frac{n}{6} \rfloor$

$$e_\infty(0) = \begin{cases} \lfloor \frac{n-3}{2} \rfloor + n \text{ if } s \text{ is odd} \\ \lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \rfloor + n \text{ if } s \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

$$e_\infty(1) = \begin{cases} \lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \rfloor + n \text{ if } s \text{ is odd} \\ \lfloor \frac{n-3}{2} \rfloor + n \text{ if } s \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

Hence ladder L_n is S_4 difference cordial graph.

Theorem 3.6. Slanting ladder SL_n is S_4 difference cordial graph.

Proof. Let $V(SL_n) = \{v'_\beta, v''_\beta : 1 \leq \beta \leq n\}$ and $E(SL_n) = \{v'_\beta v'_{\beta+1}, v''_\beta v''_{\beta+1}, v'_\beta v''_{\beta+1} : 1 \leq \beta \leq n-1\}$. Define $\alpha : V(SL_n) \rightarrow S_4$ as follows:

$$\alpha(v'_\beta) = \begin{cases} k & \text{if } \beta \equiv 1 \pmod{12} \\ l & \text{if } \beta \equiv 2 \pmod{12} \\ n & \text{if } \beta \equiv 3 \pmod{12} \\ p & \text{if } \beta \equiv 4 \pmod{12} \\ q & \text{if } \beta \equiv 5 \pmod{12} \\ d & \text{if } \beta \equiv 6 \pmod{12} \\ s & \text{if } \beta \equiv 7 \pmod{12} \\ u & \text{if } \beta \equiv 8 \pmod{12} \\ v & \text{if } \beta \equiv 9 \pmod{12} \\ h & \text{if } \beta \equiv 10 \pmod{12} \\ i & \text{if } \beta \equiv 11 \pmod{12} \\ r & \text{if } \beta \equiv 0 \pmod{12} \end{cases}$$

$$\alpha(v''_\beta) = \begin{cases} g & \text{if } \beta \equiv 1 \pmod{12} \\ m & \text{if } \beta \equiv 2 \pmod{12} \\ a & \text{if } \beta \equiv 3 \pmod{12} \\ o & \text{if } \beta \equiv 4 \pmod{12} \\ b & \text{if } \beta \equiv 5 \pmod{12} \\ c & \text{if } \beta \equiv 6 \pmod{12} \\ f & \text{if } \beta \equiv 7 \pmod{12} \\ t & \text{if } \beta \equiv 8 \pmod{12} \\ e & \text{if } \beta \equiv 9 \pmod{12} \\ w & \text{if } \beta \equiv 10 \pmod{12} \\ x & \text{if } \beta \equiv 11 \pmod{12} \\ j & \text{if } \beta \equiv 0 \pmod{12} \end{cases}$$

It is observed as

$$e_\alpha(0) = \begin{cases} 3 \binom{n-1}{2} & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \\ 3 \lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \rfloor + 1 \text{ or } 3 \lceil \frac{n-1}{2} \rceil + 2 & \text{if } n \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

and

$$e_\alpha(1) = \begin{cases} 3 \binom{n-1}{2} & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \\ 3 \lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \rfloor + 1 \text{ or } 3 \lceil \frac{n-1}{2} \rceil + 2 & \text{if } n \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

Hence SL_n is S_4 difference cordial graph.

Theorem 3.7. The graph $L_n \odot K_1$ is S_4 difference cordial graph.

Proof. Let $V(L_n \odot K_1) = \{v^1_\beta, v^2_\beta, v^3_\beta, v^4_\beta : 1 \leq \beta \leq n\}$ and

$$E(L_n \odot K_1) = \{v^1_\beta v^2_\beta, v^2_\beta v^3_\beta, v^3_\beta v^4_\beta : 1 \leq \beta \leq n\} \cup \{v^2_\beta v^2_{\beta+1}, v^3_\beta v^3_{\beta+1} : 1 \leq \beta \leq n-1\}.$$

Define $\alpha : V(L_n \odot K_1) \rightarrow S_4$ as follows:

$$\alpha(v^1_\beta) = \begin{cases} k & \text{if } \beta \equiv 1 \pmod{6} \\ m & \text{if } \beta \equiv 2 \pmod{6} \\ s & \text{if } \beta \equiv 3 \pmod{6} \\ g & \text{if } \beta \equiv 4 \pmod{6} \\ u & \text{if } \beta \equiv 5 \pmod{6} \\ w & \text{if } \beta \equiv 0 \pmod{6} \end{cases} \quad \alpha(v^2_\beta) = \begin{cases} a & \text{if } \beta \equiv 1 \pmod{6} \\ n & \text{if } \beta \equiv 2 \pmod{6} \\ o & \text{if } \beta \equiv 3 \pmod{6} \\ q & \text{if } \beta \equiv 4 \pmod{6} \\ v & \text{if } \beta \equiv 5 \pmod{6} \\ x & \text{if } \beta \equiv 0 \pmod{6} \end{cases}$$

$$\alpha(v^3_\beta) = \begin{cases} b & \text{if } \beta \equiv 1 \pmod{6} \\ c & \text{if } \beta \equiv 2 \pmod{6} \\ p & \text{if } \beta \equiv 3 \pmod{6} \\ r & \text{if } \beta \equiv 4 \pmod{6} \\ h & \text{if } \beta \equiv 5 \pmod{6} \\ j & \text{if } \beta \equiv 0 \pmod{6} \end{cases} \quad \alpha(v^4_\beta) = \begin{cases} l & \text{if } \beta \equiv 1 \pmod{6} \\ d & \text{if } \beta \equiv 2 \pmod{6} \\ f & \text{if } \beta \equiv 3 \pmod{6} \\ t & \text{if } \beta \equiv 4 \pmod{6} \\ i & \text{if } \beta \equiv 5 \pmod{6} \\ e & \text{if } \beta \equiv 0 \pmod{6} \end{cases}$$

In this type of labeling pattern, we observe that

$$e_\infty(0) = \begin{cases} 2n + \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor - 1 & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{5n}{2} - 1 & \text{if } n \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

$$e_\infty(1) = \begin{cases} 2n + \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{5n}{2} - 1 & \text{if } n \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

Thus the graph $L_n \odot K_1$ is S_4 difference cordial graph.

Theorem 3.8. The graph $TL_n \odot K_1$ is S_4 difference cordial graph.

Proof. Let $V(TL_n \odot K_1) = \{v_\beta^1, v_\beta^2, v_\beta^3, v_\beta^4 : 1 \leq \beta \leq n\}$ and

$$E(TL_n \odot K_1) = \{v_\beta^1 v_\beta^2, v_\beta^2 v_\beta^3, v_\beta^3 v_\beta^4 : 1 \leq \beta \leq n\} \cup \{v_\beta^2 v_{\beta+1}^2, v_\beta^3 v_{\beta+1}^3, v_\beta^4 v_{\beta+1}^4 : 1 \leq \beta \leq n-1\}.$$

Define $\infty : V(TL_n \odot K_1) \rightarrow S_4$ as follows:

$$\infty(v_\beta^1) = \begin{cases} k & \text{if } \beta \equiv 1 \pmod{6} \\ m & \text{if } \beta \equiv 2 \pmod{6} \\ t & \text{if } \beta \equiv 3 \pmod{6} \\ u & \text{if } \beta \equiv 4 \pmod{6} \\ g & \text{if } \beta \equiv 5 \pmod{6} \\ i & \text{if } \beta \equiv 0 \pmod{6} \end{cases} \quad \infty(v_\beta^2) = \begin{cases} a & \text{if } \beta \equiv 1 \pmod{6} \\ n & \text{if } \beta \equiv 2 \pmod{6} \\ o & \text{if } \beta \equiv 3 \pmod{6} \\ f & \text{if } \beta \equiv 4 \pmod{6} \\ h & \text{if } \beta \equiv 5 \pmod{6} \\ j & \text{if } \beta \equiv 0 \pmod{6} \end{cases}$$

$$\infty(v_\beta^3) = \begin{cases} b & \text{if } \beta \equiv 1 \pmod{6} \\ c & \text{if } \beta \equiv 2 \pmod{6} \\ p & \text{if } \beta \equiv 3 \pmod{6} \\ q & \text{if } \beta \equiv 4 \pmod{6} \\ v & \text{if } \beta \equiv 5 \pmod{6} \\ x & \text{if } \beta \equiv 0 \pmod{6} \end{cases} \quad \infty(v_\beta^4) = \begin{cases} l & \text{if } \beta \equiv 1 \pmod{6} \\ s & \text{if } \beta \equiv 2 \pmod{6} \\ d & \text{if } \beta \equiv 3 \pmod{6} \\ r & \text{if } \beta \equiv 4 \pmod{6} \\ w & \text{if } \beta \equiv 5 \pmod{6} \\ e & \text{if } \beta \equiv 0 \pmod{6} \end{cases}$$

Let $n = 6z + \gamma$ where $z \geq 0$ and $0 \leq \gamma \leq 5$. We observe that,

$$e_\infty(0) = 3(6z + \gamma) - 2 \text{ and } e_\infty(1) = 3(6z + \gamma) - 1.$$

Thus the graph $TL_n \odot K_1$ is S_4 difference cordial graph.

Theorem 3.8. The graph $P_n \odot 2K_1$ is S_4 difference cordial graph.

Proof. Let $V(P_n \odot 2K_1) = \{v_\beta^1, v_\beta^2, v_\beta^3 : 1 \leq \beta \leq n\}$ and

$$E(P_n \odot 2K_1) = \{v_\beta^1 v_\beta^2, v_\beta^2 v_\beta^3 : 1 \leq \beta \leq n\} \cup \{v_\beta^2 v_{\beta+1}^2 : 1 \leq \beta \leq n-1\}.$$

Define $\infty : V(P_n \odot 2K_1) \rightarrow S_4$ as follows:

$$\infty(v_\beta^1) = \begin{cases} a & \text{if } \beta \equiv 1 \pmod{8} \\ e & \text{if } \beta \equiv 2 \pmod{8} \\ k & \text{if } \beta \equiv 3 \pmod{8} \\ l & \text{if } \beta \equiv 4 \pmod{8} \\ m & \text{if } \beta \equiv 5 \pmod{8} \\ u & \text{if } \beta \equiv 6 \pmod{8} \\ o & \text{if } \beta \equiv 7 \pmod{8} \\ p & \text{if } \beta \equiv 0 \pmod{8} \end{cases} \quad \infty(v_\beta^2) = \begin{cases} b & \text{if } \beta \equiv 1 \pmod{8} \\ c & \text{if } \beta \equiv 2 \pmod{8} \\ f & \text{if } \beta \equiv 3 \pmod{8} \\ g & \text{if } \beta \equiv 4 \pmod{8} \\ i & \text{if } \beta \equiv 5 \pmod{8} \\ v & \text{if } \beta \equiv 6 \pmod{8} \\ x & \text{if } \beta \equiv 7 \pmod{8} \\ q & \text{if } \beta \equiv 0 \pmod{8} \end{cases}$$

$$\infty(v_\beta^3) = \begin{cases} s & \text{if } \beta \equiv 1 \pmod{8} \\ d & \text{if } \beta \equiv 2 \pmod{8} \\ l & \text{if } \beta \equiv 3 \pmod{8} \\ h & \text{if } \beta \equiv 4 \pmod{8} \\ n & \text{if } \beta \equiv 5 \pmod{8} \\ w & \text{if } \beta \equiv 6 \pmod{8} \\ j & \text{if } \beta \equiv 7 \pmod{8} \\ r & \text{if } \beta \equiv 0 \pmod{8} \end{cases}$$

Consider $n = 8z + \gamma$ where $z \geq 0$ and $0 \leq \gamma \leq 7$. In this type of labeling pattern,

$$e_{\infty}(0) = \begin{cases} n + \frac{n}{2} & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \\ n + \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor & \text{if } n \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

$$e_{\infty}(1) = \begin{cases} n + \frac{n}{2} - 1 & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \\ n + \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor & \text{if } n \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

Therefore $P_n \odot 2K_1$ is S_4 difference cordial graph.

4 Conclusion

The cordial labeling of graphs has been a topic of research for 35 years and it has many properties to be found. It is already settled that many graphs are group Q_8 difference cordial and group S_3 remainder cordial. Finally in this paper the new concept of group S_4 difference cordial labeling have been defined. We also proved that path, cycle, comb, bistar, crown and ladder related graphs admit group S_4 difference cordial labeling.

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